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“FROM HISTORY TO HERITAGE: IMPROVING COMMUNITY AWARENESS FOR GUIUAN’S CULTURAL PRESERVATION”

Guiuan, situated at the southernmost tip of Eastern Samar in the Eastern Visayas, Philippines, is not just a place offering a retreat to the Pacific with beautiful, white-sand beaches – it is full of remarkable, undeniable history. From its participation in the early stages of Spanish colonization to its crucial role in World War II, Guiuan claims a rich heritage that has shaped its community narratives. However, as modernization, natural calamities, weathering, and man-made destruction, such as illegal logging, irresponsible mining practices, among others, continue to threaten these rare and valuable cultural assets, making it increasingly clear that promoting community awareness and taking collective action for the preservation of these cultural and historical remnants is vital.

Guiuan’s historical landmarks are proof of its unique journey. From Homonhon Island’s role in the Magellan Landing, which continue to contest the province of Cebu on its claims regarding the matter, to the Immaculate Conception Church, located at the center of the municipality, emulating Baroque architecture and interior design, evidence of it being built in the 18th century, outsourcing locally available materials such as various seashells, used in decorating its altar. The town’s coastlines once served as an entry point for American troops during World War II, marked by remnants of airstrips and bunkers -spread out. The now-called Jetty, part of Brgy. Hollywood – Jetty, located in Guiuan East district, was once part of the airstrip, the Guiuan Aviation runway – used during the aftermath of Super Typhoon Haiyan/ Yolanda in sending both local and international aid to the survivors, to flying in tourists from across the world. To the remaining concrete airstrip parts running from Brgy. Cantahay (Guiuan South) to Brgy. Sapao (Guiuan East) – which marks the end of the runway. The route from Jetty to Brgy. Sapao is evidence of the existence of this once majestic airstrip that could have housed more than a hundred planes and jets. Another landmark, located at Brgy. Ngolos, located at Guiuan South District, are remnants of a World War II US Naval Base. Concrete floors, bunkers, where modern houses are built on top of. A concrete flooring used for car-washing for US Army Jeeps can still be found inside Cogon Elementary School, in Brgy. Cogon, Guiuan North District. A ruined lighthouse tower and other naval-base remnants can still be found in Sulu-an Island, Guiuan South District. Manicani Island, an island in Guiuan East District, also played its role, serving as a military–naval base during World War II. Tubabao Island, located in the Guiuan North District, also served as a Refugee Camp for white Russians. These places are not just attractions; they are cultural gems that anchor the town and its people’s identity and collective memory.

As the saying goes, “*Ang taong hindi marunong lumingon sa pinaggalingan, ay hindi makakarating sa paroroonan*” or translated in English means, “An individual who does not know how to look back where they came from, will never reach their destination”, means that we should never forget where we came from, we should never forget our beginnings, how we got here, the journey of getting where we are at present, these emphasizes the importance of gratitude, humility, and recognizing one’s roots as basis and realization of future accomplishments. Thus, the importance of preserving Guiuan’s rich culture, by improving practices on cultural and educational tourism, starting with seminars, forums, and tours for Guiuan locals before opening tourism for non-Guiuanons, for Guiuanons to be well-versed on local tourism and become guides, and references once Guiuan is opened to the rest of the world, and for Guiuananons, working outside Guiuan, may it be the rest of the Philippines or abroad, to proudly tell the story of their birthplace, their home.

Aside from cultural and educational tourism, there are several other avenues for improving community participation in preserving Guiuan’s rich history, including education and storytelling – through curriculum integration, via schools, and encouraging elders to tell their stories to the next generation. Another is heritage mapping, where residents can participate in mapping historical sites, tagging oral histories, and documenting traditional practices. Community-led restoration, heritage festivals, and partnerships shall also be done to help mobilize community efforts. Currently, a historical exhibit done in Luzon has been participated in by Guiuan LGU, and a Guiuan Museum is currently being completed, cementing the start of Guiuan’s awareness of its local history.

The journey from history to heritage is collective, as it cannot be done by a single individual or group. When Guiuan’s residents and locals are equipped with information and tools to defend their cultural legacy – the reminder of their standing to the world, the improvement from passive observers and bystanders into active protectors takes root. This empowerment ensures that Guiuan’s place in history will be , and that, for generations to come, the stories, these historical sites will be preserved, honored, revered – the soul of Guiuan will remain vibrant and distinguished. Preserving this heritage is not just about community awareness and safeguarding the past – it is about enriching the present and ensuring a future for all Guiuananons.